

TC FOR BE

TRANSFORMATIVE CHANGE
FOR BIODIVERSITY & EQUITY

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1. Introduction

This document explains some of the key theory and concepts underpinning the project and specifically this exercise WP 5.2 on rural imaginaries and provides a more detailed methodology and timetable.

2. Conceptual background

Below is an overview of key concepts relevant to social imaginaries and future-making for TCforBE project. Note that this activity is linked to others in WP 5 and the rest of the project.

Transformative Change

Transformative change concepts are evolving and are contested, but a common theme in recent literature is that it involves deep values, knowledge and ontological shifts, which themselves require the exertion of power. TCforBE is exploring how processes which support democratic co-production and exploration of TC pathways with diverse actors in study landscapes, which are part of telecoupled agrofood systems.

A definition for the project is as follows:

- *Radical changes in structures and everyday practices facilitating greater sustainability and justice, achieved through deep shifts in values, ontologies and epistemologies and requiring exertion of material and discursive power by actors resisting and overcoming the orthodoxies and hegemonies which generate socio-ecological damage.*

TC may not be feasible in all conditions, including in our project localities. One of the aspects that is important in this project is whether there is space for TC explorations and actions, given the level of power inequalities which frequently characterise such telecoupled landscapes. Where multi-stakeholder learning is deemed not to be feasible, we may need to reconsider and conduct workshops with aligned and non-aligned groups (with respect to biodiversity and equity).

It is important to have good linkages to national scale processes (or beyond) – i.e. to identify if there are national policy or strategy processes on biodiversity or related areas e.g. agriculture, where project findings can be of relevance.

Participatory approaches have long been important in giving voice to marginalized perspectives, for example, many Indigenous Peoples and local communities. Additionally, communities are not monolithic but include many lines of differentiation and intersectionality. Understanding and engaging such diverse views within communities is thus important.

This project aims to address this by facilitating community voice work, leading into multi-stakeholder social learning, and by eliciting and co-generating plural perspectives of transformative change for biodiversity and equity related to landscapes producing telecoupled agrifoods exported to the EU as the broad topic, within which local learning priorities can be identified.

Participatory approaches have limitations. They vary in the extent to which they engage people in shaping action research processes, and are critiqued for being a Western driven approach, that does not address deeper political patterns of thinking and being, which are infused in systems, structures and path dependencies, i.e. there are risks that such approaches do not address prevailing dominant worldviews and values, and do not allow space for community participation in design of research and development. Facilitating community voice at an early stage and eliciting current and future rural imaginaries in this process creates opportunities to amplify local and Indigenous worldviews and values and for participation in future-making processes. It is also the case that in forest frontiers, notions of modernity and instrumental priorities already prevail and align with dominant perspectives and may need to be challenged for sustainability transformations. So it is important for country research teams to reflect upon what is feasible and to adapt appropriately.

Making space for plural perspectives, especially those that challenge dominant perspectives, is key to transformative change and transdisciplinary approaches. Certain worldviews and values (colonial modernities, capitalism etc) dominate in different parts in different ways across the world, sidelining plural

values and worldviews. The project aims to facilitate multi-stakeholder social learning, drawing upon a diversity of perspectives.

Imaginarities

This section defines the term 'imaginarities' and explains how it is relevant to the TCforBE project.

Social imaginaries are the shared frameworks of meaning that influence how individuals and communities perceive and experience their social and ecological worlds, including their values, norms, and cultural practices. These imaginaries are often implicit and deeply ingrained in a society's institutions (formal and informal rules, laws and norms), influencing how people understand themselves and their relationships with others.

Diverse social theorists have explored the notion of 'imaginarities', and their role in shaping individual subjectivities and societal change processes. Subjectivities are how individuals experience and interpret their own identities, perceptions, emotions and understandings of the world shaped by cultural, historical, social, political and personal factors. Societal change processes, including ongoing transformations, are also key in cultivating collectives and affiliations.¹

Various authors note that respect, reciprocity and reverence for cultural and linguistic diversity is important to achieve goals of equity and justice. Respect for diverse cultural imaginaries while fostering unity and common purpose, and specifically recognizing the socio-cultural imaginaries of diverse marginalized groups is a common theme.

Latterly, this includes attention to the often unrecognized agency and labour of non-human species. Of late, this has included attention to non-human species and their agency and perspectives in co-creating landscapes as part of assemblages of the human, non-human and inhuman.

Box 1: More than human, assemblage theory and multi-species justice and TCforBE

- Places are made creatively by assemblages of entangled humans, non-humans (plants, animals, microorganisms, phenomena, technologies etc).
- Decentres the human subject, to focus on life as continually unfolding relations (dynamic and relational nature of entities their interactions within complex systems (Deleuze and Guattari)
- Recognizing the agency and labour of non-human species
- Leads to focus on multi-species justice in understanding human-nature relations, which itself is critical for a project on biodiversity and equity.

It is important to be attentive to the ways in which different groups are discriminated against, often along multiple lines of differentiation e.g. caste, class, ethnicity, age, sexuality etc, which means that it is important to understand the lived experiences of different groups (women, men, different ethnicities, classes, ages, generations) and as the forms of discrimination are multiple and intersecting (intersectionality). Some authors have begun to include non-human species in intersectional thinking.

Other scholars have focused on imaginaries in relation to diverse contexts. For example, urban settings (Sassen, de Certau), foregrounding different themes such as role of narratives and storytelling in social and cultural imaginaries (Ricoeur), the role of normative ideals and moral imaginaries in driving political and social change (Fraser), digital communication and contemporary social imaginaries (Castells), global imaginaries and imagined worlds in 'scapes' linked to globalisation (Appadurai), in shaping national

¹ For example, Castoriadis emphasized social imaginary significations or symbolic meanings as being important in the creation and transformation of societies and institutions (ref). Taylor (ref) argued that people's self-understanding and their affiliation with specific communities are shaped by and constructed using the narratives, symbols, and values associated with social imaginaries.

identities and national states (Anderson), and the use of conceptual frames in shaping political thought (Lakoff).

Imaginaries are not solely something in the mind and are distinct from the imagination, co-constituting change processes in unfolding socio-material processes. Imaginaries relate to the interaction between *mental* constructs, beliefs and ideas that are created by individuals and societies, they also interact with and have interdependencies with materialities (biophysical, technology, infrastructure, the environment etc) in complex, mutually influencing ways (societal change is a continual unfolding of relations – West et al, ref).

Diverse values of nature are relevant to understanding human-nature relations. Biocultural (i.e. addressing interlinked biological and cultural factors) imaginaries gives attention to interconnected biological and cultural diversity in imaginary development, addressing not only instrumental (e.g. utility to humans) and intrinsic values (inherent worth of nature), but also relational values – i.e. spiritual and sacred values (IPBES, 2022). Indeed, beyond thinking of these three types of values of nature (identified by IPBES), other authors have argued that relations are inherent in all aspects of these identified ‘uses’ of nature in many Indigenous societies (refs), i.e. nature is kin in many communities (i.e. a mountain may be understood as kin) (Foggins et al), but there are also important relational principles in livelihood activities in Indigenous communities (e.g. if an animal presents itself to some Inuit cultures, it is deemed ready to be killed for food, and prayers are said in recognition).

Some species are culturally important for Indigenous and local communities, and that these may differ from the species prioritized by scientists. Cultural keystone species and places have been identified and monitored in some Indigenous and scientific collaborations. In relational thinking, the focus of study is not separate components of nature, with scientific taxonomies, but the relations between e.g. how people and whales shape each other’s behaviour in a certain context. The project has selected landscapes based on their biodiversity importance as well as telecoupled connections to Europe, involving key commodities e.g. tea, coffee, cocoa, bananas, oil palm and avocados. But the aim in the imaginaries work is to take a more open stance, rather than to focus on specific commodities as the entry point. It is assumed, that if these commodities are important in the imaginaries of those participating then they will emerge unforced during discussions. [This is certainly the case in the Kenyan example]. By articulating different imaginaries of landscape pasts, presents and futures, values and perspectives, this may elicit dominant orthodoxies and hegemonies which can be challenged for more transformative change – or not if the transformative change space is too closed.

Methods for researching imaginaries should ideally seek to unpack some of these different ways of responding to and understanding human-nature relations. This includes being firstly aware of the imposition of dominant perspectives that nature is primarily a resource, something to be used and controlled for human benefit (Adams and Mulligan, 2003; Arora and Stirling, 2023). More biocentric approaches emphasize the worth of nature on its own account. Pluricentric approaches consider the interconnectedness and interdependence of all living beings (IPBES, 2022). See Figure below from IPBES (2022 Values Assessment), which distinguishes between anthropocentric, biocentric and pluricentric perspectives, with the latter gaining increasing attention in biodiversity research.

Figure 1: IPBES Values Typology
(Values Assessment, 2022)

Imaginaries methodologies are multiple and varied. Generally they seek to explore the *collective* beliefs, values, symbols, and narratives, that shape the way a social group, society or culture perceives itself and its place in the world – including its relations with or existence as and entangled with nature. *In TCforBE we will focus on working with communities and social groups to explore landscape imaginaries.*

Values can be distinguished in terms of broad values (e.g. underlying worldviews and cosmologies) and specific values (e.g. applying values in response to specific policy or management decisions) (IPBES, 2022). Values will be contested in any context, but often broad, underlying worldviews and shared collective beliefs, values, symbols and narratives which create social cohesion change less rapidly.

Exploring imaginaries through arts-based (ABM) methods is increasingly common. Arts-based approaches may help to engage and challenge participants in learning. Participatory photography is one example of a methodology, which is known to have value in engaging communities by engaging in a deeper way through emotions and can help us to see and be in the world differently– as part of transformative change efforts. ABM range from artists direct responses and ‘serious play’ in relation to complex societal challenges to artists facilitating participatory processes with stakeholders and communities in ways that may be quite unusual and disrupting of dominant norms, to artists working closely with communities to support them to conduct citizen arts. Methods include visual methods such as painting, written such as fiction, oral storytelling, and sonic / audio arts. These can engage participants

more deeply by connecting through emotions, elicit and co-generate new connectivities and care, and has the potential to unlearn colonial modernities and allow for decoloniality perspectives. **Storytelling, especially, is gaining ground to allow Indigenous and local communities to frame their own narratives** (Bishu, add various refs, Baobab example of African storytelling) in ways that may stem from their own experience. It is interesting to consider in a context of a longstanding colonial histories and post-colonial forest frontier land pressures, how far different values of nature exist.

Senses of place

'Sense of place' concepts explore how people perceive, experience and **make attachments to meanings in specific locations** or spaces. *In TCforBE we focus on selected places we have framed as study landscapes.* Tuan (1977) explored subjective experiences of places and their personal and cultural meanings. Seamon (2000; 2012) highlights the lived experience of individuals in their environments and how embodied meanings are woven into our experiences of place. Cresswell (2004) foregrounds identity, memory and power in relation to place-making. Massey (2005) takes a relational and dynamic conceptualisation of places, emphasizing the interconnectedness of locations within broader social and political contexts.

Instrumental dependencies on places include food (food growing, harvesting, processing and cooking etc) but there are also symbolic dimensions of food for example, including relational values in all these food-related activities and aspects of conviviality as well as subsistence. Rather than focusing upon the individual, it is possible to attend to the symbolism and meanings imbued in key relationships in a shared location (see Pollini, 2005; – perspectives which will also vary according to social groups).

A sense of belonging to a group or place is key to societal imaginaries. In recent years, social science research has increasingly looked at places as not being humans with passive nature in the background, but at places as being *processes* in which assemblages of the human and non-human (see Latour, refs) interact in continually unfolding relations, often in highly inter-dependent ways. Living creatures experience such processes in layers of relations (lived experiences) and subjectivities are formed and place attachments made by different actors over time as relations unfold. Changes occur when actors resist and change, but often also reinforce values and relations (Foucault). Such processes are imbued with power and meaning. Care (by actors in assemblages) for places – understood as relational assemblages – can be regenerated or undermined over time, as power dynamics are enacted. Colonial modernity and capitalist worldviews tend to undermine such interdependencies and care ethics (refs).

There are many ways to research sense of place, place-based values and care ethics.

A key area requiring more attention, is not only how people cognitively relate to a place, i.e. what they say and think about it, but also what they feel and experience about a place. Growing bodies of work emphasize a) that nature and humans are not rigidly separate, but entangled and interdependent, b) humans not only think about the world, but sense and feel it, and further, c) other living entities also sense, feel and think (moving beyond an 'anthropocentric perspective') and have agency.

Box 1 Example of participatory methods to approach human-nature-place relations.

Researchers Pramova et al (ref) explored human-nature relations through a more systematic, participatory exploration of sensing, feeling, thinking. Pramova et al (ref. p353-4) distinguish between:

- **Settings** (living and non-living ecosystem components such as trees, mountains), broader scenic images (e.g. vastness of the landscape) and more ephemeral elements (e.g. gentle morning breeze, sunset light and colours) (after Farber and Hall (2007)', and 'human-modified environments such as agro-ecosystems and landscapes containing buildings (Russell et al., 2013).
- **'Activities'**, - metaphysical and intellectual interactions such as dreaming and imagining, inspired by 'channels of experience' (Russell et al., 2013), as well as structured and unstructured physical interactions such as hiking, playing freely and swimming (Ives et al., 2017).
- **'Nature experiences'** - expand on the internal dimensions of experience (sensation, cognition and affect) from the Experiencing Nature Model of Linzmayer et al. (2014), which is based on psychology and neurobiology literature (Barrett & Bliss-Moreau, 2009; Nelson, 2009; Schore, 2003). People respond to sensory stimulation from the external environment, but they also generate multi-sensory images within themselves (Agapito et al., 2013; Hirschman & Hoolbrook, 1982; MacInnis & Price, 1987), which can be historical (recalling an event) or imagined (reconfiguring known sensory elements through imagination).
- **'Sensory experiences'**, we included experiences related to the five exteroceptive senses (sight, hearing, smell, taste and touch) and those related to movement (kinaesthetic) and gravity (Tuan, 1974). We also include perceptions formed by processing and interpreting external stimuli captured by our senses (Agapito et al., 2013; Goldstein & Brockmole, 2016; Ingold, 2000; Zimbardo et al., 2017). Our internal realm determines our perceptions of the world, as these mechanisms of processing and interpretation are shaped by experience, knowledge, values and emotional states (Agapito et al., 2013; Wilson-Mendenhall & Barsalou, 2016; Zimbardo et al., 2012).
- **Cognition:** It is impossible to separate the interdependent neural and psychological processes and delineate where perception stops and cognition begins (Leventhal & Scherer, 1987). But for practical analysis, we consider 'Cognitive experiences' to be conceptual and reflective processes such as thinking (Clare & Schiller, 2016; Leventhal & Scherer, 1987). These experiences involve values, attitudes, knowledge and beliefs and include memories, aesthetics, spiritual thoughts, nostalgia or inspiration (Farber & Hall, 2007; Ives et al., 2017; Williams & Harvey, 2001).
- **'Affective experiences'** include moods, feelings and emotions (Clare & Schiller, 2016; Ortony et al., 1987; Zylstra et al., 2014). 'Affect' is a broad concept involving different kinds of valenced judgements from good/pleasant to bad/unpleasant (Clare et al., 1987; Clare & Schiller, 2016; Ortony et al., 1987). All emotions are affective, but not all affective conditions are emotions (Clare et al., 1987; Ortony et al., 1987). Emotions are internal, affective mental states that include dimensions of stimulus and valence, with emotional episodes being complex, structured events (Farber & Hall, 2007; Goldie, 2000; Lambie & Marcel, 2002; Ortony et al., 1987; Russell & Barrett, 1999). Emotions are episodic because they occur following a specific event or stimulus and are structured because they form part of a narrative or sequence containing actions, events, thoughts and feelings (Goldie, 2000). We consider feelings and emotions as affective experiences, recognizing that it is not practical to distinguish them. Lastly, it is important to point out that sensation, emotion and cognition are integrated in experience and the internal processing thereof, making it difficult determine where one internal process ends and another begins..'

They analyse these via a set of interviews with diverse actors in a place (ice-breaking discussions on the region and followed by semi-structured interviews and coding) using 'grounded theory' (Strauss and Corbin, 1994) to analyse imageries of participants, based on the emergence of repeated concepts and types of experiences, rather than using an *a priori* typology. Classified each term into the five dimensions of the framework and did coding and analysis.

Exploring how people feel and sense places is therefore important in understanding values, ontologies, and epistemologies, revealing diverse perspectives and realities, and this also extends to new work to explore how other species of plants, animals and micro-organisms sense, feel and think. While sentience and intention may vary, science increasingly shows sentience and interdependencies in nature, which have been often overlooked in anthropocentric perspectives. This area of work is called the 'more-than-human' – it looks at the diverse assemblages of actors that inter-relate in place, all having (varying levels of) agency, intention and impact/responsibilities. Further, living organisms all have their own needs and subjective interpretations of the world around them ('umwelt' being the area of the world with significant and meaning for a particular organism based on its biology and needs (Von Uexkül, ref; Sebeok, ref).

Future-making and recognizing the past.

Approaches to future-making are evolving. While conventional approaches include the development of scenarios and models (as explored in TCforBE WP 1), these also have limitations. Foresight work has gained increasing traction as well. However, such approaches tend to address a relatively narrow range of future options, obscuring the many assumptions upon which they rest and have been critiqued for reinforcing notions of modernity and progress, while sidelining alternative future-making realities and practices. Thus WP5 uses alternative future making methods and concepts.

Understanding place-making requires recognition of collective pasts, and that these can be negotiated and changing. Feola et al (2023) provide a framework for exploring active processes of place-making by actors, which involves interviewing stakeholders to unpack visions not only of the future, but also of the past and present. Place making is part of change processes and can be defined as "the process of reproducing, eliminating, and/or modifying the structures, identities, meanings, geographies, positionalities, and power relations associated with a given place" (Murphy, 2015:84). Central to place making is place framing, i.e. the creation of particular visions or imaginaries for the current or future development of places (Murphy, 2015, cited by Feola et al, 2023). Place making involves collective memories, place framing and future visions.

- **Place making** is when different actors mobilize collective or shared 'place bundles' to achieve specific social and political goals. These are not necessarily accurate representations of a place, but they serve as tools for advancing particular agendas.
- **Place framing** involves the strategic selection and assemblage of symbolic and material elements/ physical and social features to construct an understanding of place and seek to legitimize it, sometimes leading to the formation of coalitions or resistance against specific political and social ideas.
- **Collective memory** is an active process of reconstructing the past in the context of the present, influenced by the interests, mental models and needs of present societies and dominant frames and can play a role in social cohesion. Memories are shaped by social filters and norms of remembering, which shape events into intelligible structures with plotlines, perceived density of events, perceptions of progression, and perceived continuity and discontinuity, which shape how the past is understood and used to envision the future.

Figure 1: Feola, G., M. K. Goodman, J. Suzunaga, J. Soler, (2023) 'Collective memories, place-framing and the politics of imaginary futures in sustainability transitions and transformations'.

This framework can be used to inform stakeholder interviews and the analysis of the data collected. Feola et al (2023) have used this approach in a peri-urban area of a city in Colombia to explore politicized justifications of specific forms of socio-material development, uses and sustainability. In the Mau Forest context, smallholder agriculture, conservation, plantations and urban development are all activities and pressures competing for space, and likely supported by actors' narratives. modelling and western oriented foresight methods, to engage with plural forms of knowledge and ways of being in exploring futures – which also has implications for methods.

Decolonising future-making praxis is becoming a strong theme, although practice is only just emerging. Use of symbols and storytelling are increasingly seen as being key in Indigenous Research Methodologies (Chilisa, ref). Bisht (2017) identifies the dominance of western perspectives as they 'colonise' most contemporary futures explorations. Alternative methods include storytelling futures for the scenario generation phase of foresight processes. She adapts the culturally inclusive Kaavad storytelling tradition of India and gives an alternative framework informed by non-Western forms of knowing, doing and being. She concludes that the proposed method 'shows transformative visions of the future that reflect authentic worldviews of participants' while celebrating epistemological plurality. Similarly, Terry et al (2024) present a very similar argument from an African perspective, again pointing to different notions of time and emphasize the importance of recognizing pasts, including those that are unrecognized, unreported or uncertain. Terry et al (2024) argue that African storytelling foregrounds three categories of futures thinking that have yet to be incorporated into foresight, scenarios and models processes: future as powerful collective-making, future as healing for multispecies justice and future for diversity and ancestry.

Figure 2: Entangled Time Tree

Terry et al, 2024

Perspectives in any community or landscape will vary on traditional knowledge, spiritual perspectives and sacred spaces, particularly in contexts of rapid social change (e.g. forest frontiers facing degradation, plantation establishment and modernization processes). Further, such beliefs take time to explore, and need to be sensitively handled and ideally are based on strong anthropological research and ethnographic skills. However, good participatory research skills can be used to a certain extent, and we will be collaborating with these groups over a number of months and years which also provides opportunities to strengthen relationships.

TCforB: Why imaginaries?

In this section, we explain why the project is firstly exploring imaginaries, with a broad lens and participatory approach. In the TCforBE project, we are concerned with agrofood systems and the distant connections that these increasingly involve, with export commodities grown in specific places, and transported to distant places for consumption, traversing different governance systems and with, often invisible, negative impacts as well as positive ones in places of production, and issues of power inequalities in value chains. Globalising value chains enable extra-territorial actors to gain control over distant localities through such resource and financial flows, as national and community control declines (Sikor et al, ref). As well as resource and financial flows, values are transmitted through such distal connections, such as conservation values (Unai et al, ref).

Why start with community voice: The aim is to co-generate transformative change pathways through transdisciplinary processes within this project – but as explained above, it is important to try and do this in ways that are more decolonised than previous efforts, hence we start with an activity that seeks to give voice to communities (broadly understood as multi-species, but also including intersectional differentiation) – to inform and influence other stakeholders in a multi-stakeholder process. Different

disciplines and methods are collaborating within the project – in this task on future (rural) imaginaries, we are seeking to apply the concepts and issues raised above to co-generate better understanding with community participants and other landscape actors, how different imaginaries are formulated and advanced, and which are sidelined yet have potential value for transformative change for biodiversity and equity. Thus, while we will be exploring the specific commodities involved (in Kenya this being tea primarily, but also avocados and pyrethrum), we start with a relatively broad entry point about how communities are connecting with nature and places, how this has changed over time and why, power relations, and how different community actors might envision futures.

The plan is that such community voices from the landscape will be shared with the social learning process later in 2024. Several methods are proposed: including Photovoice with local communities and Community Forest Associations (CFAs), with activities exploring sense of place, past and future imaginaries, and more-than-human perspectives. Elders' storytelling circle and focus group discussions with CFA and non-CFA members are also planned. This will collect a diverse range of views, although not representative. These will support wider discussion in the community and in the landscape level social learning process. This work will also complement analyses by the team on stakeholders, previous landscape interventions and landscape pressures, by a PhD student on governance and more than human perspectives, and by planned household surveys (and later enterprise and Bayesian tool activities).

3. Methodology

3.1 Overview

In this project task, we are exploring diverse (e.g. local, Indigenous, migrant, farmer, worker stakeholders in the landscape and export value chains etc) imaginaries (in contexts of landscapes that are telecoupled by global agrofood systems) to co-generate better understanding of senses of and connections to place, and how these are changing, and to begin to explore desirable futures and transformative change pathways.

Firstly, we will use Photovoice methodology. See documents from PV training for more information. Photovoice (PV) is a methodology for hearing and promoting community or stakeholder voices. There are different methodologies and processes according to different authors and trainers, including more fully participatory approaches. We are employing a participatory version, which draws upon Indigenous Research Methodologies (Chilisa, ref) and storytelling (refs) etc.

PV is a participatory research and visual methodology that allows individuals or communities to use photography to document and represent their experiences, perspectives and narratives. It is often used in social and community research to empower different, including marginalized or under-represented groups, to tell their stories and advocate for social change. Key steps include giving participants cameras or smartphones and encouraging them to take photographs of their everyday lives, experiences, challenges and aspirations. The images should reflect the issues or themes under investigation. In addition to taking photos, participants are asked to write narratives or captions that explain and provide context for the images. These narratives help convey the meaning behind the photos and the participants' perspectives. Researchers and participants engage in group discussions or workshops, during which participants share their photos and narratives with each other and the research team. These discussions allow participants to reflect upon their experiences and the significance of their images. Researchers may analyse the visual and narrative data to identify recurring themes, patterns and insights. The photographs and narratives often provide a rich source of qualitative data. PV is often used as a tool for advocacy and social change. The visual and narrative data can be shared with policymakers, community organisations and the public to raise awareness of the issues depicted and to advocate for improvements or solutions. PV has been used in various research contexts, such as public health, social justice, environmental issues, community development etc. Its value is in giving voice to individuals and communities who may or may not have been heard through traditional research methods. It can be an empowering and transformative process, enabling participants to articulate their experiences and contribute to meaningful change in their communities.

Secondly, we plan to hold an agreed number (e.g. 4 per group) of **Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)** to explore with landscape members, which will explore changing human–nature relations and landscapes.

Thirdly, we will facilitate **elders’ storytelling circle** to explore elders’ perspectives on changing human–nature relations.

Fourthly, we plan to conduct a set of **stakeholder interviews** in each landscape, using a method which draws upon Feola et al and a senses of place exercise with reflection on landscape photography.

Potential limitations and risks

Any action research, which is distinct from development project interventions risk raising expectations that cannot be met. Emphasis will be laid upon the value of learning – within the community, as well as facilitation of learning with other actors through the social learning process.

The extent to which social learning processes are possible will depend on power dynamics and the quality of facilitation etc. It also requires a minimum level of democracy allowing for deliberative processes.

Some aspects of this research are highly novel, e.g. integrating More-Than-Human perspectives in forest frontier, telecoupled landscape work is new and important, but may take time to generate an effective method.

3.2 Key steps in the methodology

Activity 1: Practical planning of imaginaries work & team training.

- Discuss key concepts for familiarisation.
- Recap on participatory principles for fieldwork (depends on skills and experience of team, but it is important to recap on issues such as taking account of appropriate times and locations for holding discussions, managing expectations and providing feedback, share principles for working with participants drawing from PV training e.g. no right or wrong in photos; all photos can be meaningful, but what a photo means can be very different for different people).
- Participatory photography training (**this is important because it is important to follow the key principles e.g. understanding ambiguities and ethics in photos and images is important**).
- Planning overall workplan and discussing analysis in advance
- Co-develop as a team an introduction for explanation in the community / forest group and potential benefits of the project. Consider risks and ethical issues as well and how to mitigate.
- Ensure that the team are clear on their roles prior to going to communities, can explain the project and its benefits, and are ready to respond to questions.
- Make sure the team has the appropriate consent processes and forms and can explain these to participants. This includes photo release process.
- Ensure that the designated roles include things like facilitation, note-taking, recording, timekeeping, etc.
- Plan for sufficient battery on phones and laptops. Ensure that all have notes and pens if needed and spare SD cards.
- Discuss language issues that might arise and how to address them.
- Team to agree on what is required in terms of providing snacks or drinks to participants etc. i.e. what is common practice and is ethical.

Activity 1: Participatory photography (Photovoice) with communities or forest association stakeholders

Selection of communities in the landscapes

As an example, in the Kenyan context, we plan to work with three or four CFAs in different parts of the Mau Forest Landscape. Four communities have been selected based on criteria of geographical spread, proximity to biodiversity forests, socio-cultural background, involvement or proximity to commodity value chains: Mara Mara (near Kericho), Bomet,

Location / Gropu	Criteria for selection
Fisherfolk	
Fruit and veg producers	
Banana smallholders	
Environmental group	For PV or perhaps stakeholder 'imaginary' interview
Indigenous	For PV or perhaps stakeholder 'imaginary' interview

Preparatory visit

Organise a preparatory visit to communities / CFAs to explain the project (material to be co-developed to ensure there is a clear explanation given of the project following ethics).

- Facilitate / request selection by community and CFA leaders of a group of max. 10 people who are willing to participate in the process. Request coverage of the diverse user groups within the CFA, also aiming for a gender balance, and a range of ages and socio-economic backgrounds. **Or invite larger meeting and conduct a selection process from the larger group to identify a group covering needed characteristics.**
- Facilitate / request selection of 8-10 people for FGD from CFA members and 8-10 for non-CFA members. Cover a range of user groups (Kenya).
- Request participation of an elders' group for a storytelling circle.
- Agree plan for the week.

Consent is required for work in all communities, but for communities that are officially recognized or self-identify as 'Indigenous' there may be specific Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) requirements.

Team Planning

Quick overview of participatory research principles and team working and the role of facilitators (exercises e.g. role play on different disciplines and photos).

Team co-design / review proposed steps in the methodology.

Reviewing ethics (including data storage – participation consent forms, image release, consent for minors in photos). How to plan discussions with communities on consent (e.g. all possible uses of photos) and copyright

Further work to refine methodology.

Planning and practising with the project digital cameras and mobile printer – use, planning photo storage etc and discussing how to engage CFA group in process, potential benefits (linking to social learning process or other pathways)

Community Fieldwork

Visit to community to begin work with CFA and non-CFA group representatives.

Introduction: Meet with community and CFA leaders to re-explain purpose of the project, methodology and consent etc.

Camera training: Exercises to build trust, familiarity with place and with the digital cameras.

- Meet participants and spend some time showing cameras and how they work and possible ethics issues that might arise.

- Explain that the camera will be left with the participant, if they are comfortable with the idea, to keep for a few days and to take photos, which they will then share and discuss with us in individual interviews. We will then be taking the cameras back to use in other communities. [We can leave copies of the photos however]
- Do practice PV exercises (e.g. short walks to practice taking photos (explaining there is no right or wrong on what to take photos of ground rules of having respect for each other's photos and perspectives etc). Visual literacy exercise. Treasure hunt exercise.

Explaining / exploring benefits of the project (seeking to identify positive / transformative change trajectories for landscapes which are exporting commodities to Europe that would have improved biodiversity and equity outcomes, strengthening stakeholder awareness and capacity on related issues and willingness to act). Specifically this activity with communities has the following envisioned benefits:

- Strengthening capacities on future-making in contexts of uncertainties over landscape dynamics and livelihoods
- Eliciting diverse perspectives and underlying broad values and ontologies (realities) of CFA (and Non CFA) community members on place, nature and food.
- Preparation to support community voice within multi-stakeholder social learning process to inform and influence decision-making processes.

Explain the PV activity 1 and ask participants to return the following day to discuss photos and develop captions. Leave digital cameras with participants. Explain the next activity for the following day and so on. Spend several days on this.

Return to community to review the photos in bilateral researcher-participant interviews, spending time to discuss the photos, capture discussions and probe on meanings, and to develop **captions with** participants for their prioritized photos.

- Ask participants to show the 2-3 photos for each of the themes identified above.
- Ask them to explain why they have taken that specific photo, what it means to them.
- Ask them to develop a caption.

Captions are not necessarily technical descriptions, but are short descriptions or responses (e.g. poems, statements of meanings and emotions). Remember meanings can be ambiguous, but they are capturing something unique perhaps and maybe powerful.

Obtaining specific consent on photos and captions at the end of the process. Share the key uses of the photos and see if they can all be used (or if any specific ones are sensitive and should not be used for certain purposes etc).

Share photos at the end with the wider group in community or group and including mini-exhibition on the walls, if appropriate.

Develop a collective collage by putting up photos together of the desired futures on the wall or computer and discussing with the group what are the connections between them (and any differences) and how to achieve the desired futures. These pathways to desired futures and the collective collage will be key to future discussions in the social learning workshops and cycle.

Reflect with the group on what they have learned during the process, if anything, in terms of the topics covered.

If appropriate, form a Whatsapp group for further structured sharing and engagement.

Explain next steps (e.g. exhibition in social learning events to inform discussions on landscape priorities).

Tasks for the Photovoice exercises

- **Activity 1:**
Please take photos which show what this place / environment / area means to you?
- **Activity 2:**

Please take photos which show the past, present and future? (several photos, captions can help, make sure you say you can capture photos that give an idea of more of what you want in the future etc?)

- **Activity 3:**

Please take photos which show a plant, animal or feature that is meaningful to you? (encounters, ongoing relations and meanings, wild and forest creatures or features especially) (photos ideally but also can bring clippings if needed).

Please take photos which show how the chosen plant, animal or feature experiences the place and changes happening?

Developing captions – an art!

Work with individuals to develop caption in the language they feel most comfortable with. We are not seeking factual descriptions, more trying to elicit and communicate feelings, senses, emotions etc to share with others. So this could be a poem, a description, a statement etc.

Facilitator helps the participant. Captions are needed for the prioritized photos for each activity:

- a) Meaning photos – choose 2 or 3 and develop the caption (remember we are not just seeking pretty photos necessarily, but something that is meaningful)/
- b) Past/present/future (expected or desired – discuss this) – choose 4 and develop the caption for each.
- c) 3 for the plant /animal / phenomena or feature e.g. river, wind, mountain – selection, experiencing changes, decisions and develop captions

Camera and photo management.

- Keep note of serial numbers and which researcher is responsible for which phones and which participant has which phone.
- All team members need to make sure named team member has lists of the properly named photos collected each day at the end of the day.
- Photos will be on the phones – Copy to multiple laptops and SD cards.
- Copy to basecamp – folder with everything – one folder for the village and sub folders per participant **each evening on return.**
- Keep a folder with the selected / priority photos.
- Also keep track of printer numbers.

List of equipment needed.

- Photovoice cameras or work with participants' own phones and symbols
- Spare SD cards
- Voice recorders
- Mobile photo printer (we purchased but the photos were a bit too small for discussions) or show to participants on laptop while they discuss (needs sufficient battery in the field). Can print overnight in photoshop potentially especially before last day.
- Flip charts and marker pens for team discussions and analysis

Activity 2: Focus Group Discussions

The **purpose** of the FGDs is to capture a wide range of perspectives from the selected communities on senses of place, how they envision pasts and futures (drawing upon local conceptions of time and relations to nature), how lives and landscape are changing, livelihoods and community production etc.

Selection: Include a range of men and women, and people of different ages and socio-economic backgrounds from the community or forest association group, hold four FGDs with 8-10 participants. (2 FGDs with women, and 2 FGDs with men). [CFAs and non-CFAs]

Conduct FGDs and elders' storytelling. If possible, conduct transect walks into the forest in between the PV activities.

Key steps

- Explain the project and potential benefits for participants, do the consent procedure. Ensure that efforts are made not to raise expectations with clear explanation of the project.
- One person should facilitate the discussion. Agree as a group what are good facilitation skills for FGDs.
- Seek to ensure that all participants have an equal chance to speak and to discuss (i.e. no participants should dominate the discussion).
- Another person should be responsible for recording the interview on their phone and taking notes as well. Explain that the recording is only to help us take notes.
- Use the checklist below and ensure that questions are probed.

See annex 7, p38 for the question checklist.

Plan for analysis

Make recordings (with consent for recording-for-notetaking) using phones or bought voice recorders XX and notes as well. Convert these into accurate transcripts of verbatim speech. These should not be summarized notes, nor written in the third person, but should be first person accurate full transcripts (e.g. 'I grow avocados...', 'I think that the forest is being degraded, but others in the community do not...').

We will then code the findings using the transcripts (using Nvivo).

Focus Group Discussions Checklist

Consent

Names, Ages

1. How did this place come to be called x? (stories of origins, beliefs, histories)
2. What are common ideas in this community about time and seasons? (ask about how elders see this, role of ancestors)
3. How are values changing and why?
4. What is changing in the environment and your surroundings? And why? Who and what is driving these changes?
5. Have you noticed any changes in the presence, absence or behaviour of wild animals and plants in the forest and area?
6. Which wild / forest plants and animals are culturally important to you? What do they need to live well alongside humans?
7. How would other plants and animals think about the future do you think?
8. How do you see the (socio-environmental) futures for this place / landscape / community? (Near and far future)? What would you like to see?
9. Are there changes in livelihood practices? If so, what? How far do livelihoods depend on the forest?

10. What are the trends in export production (e.g. tea, avocados, dairy etc) and what are the impacts on the environment?

Activity 3: Elder's Storytelling Circle

Participatory method involving a focus group discussion with checklist of questions (see annex 8). Purpose is to explore elders' perspectives on environmental change and changing human-nature relations. Similar to a FGD, ask participants of advanced age if they are able to attend a discussion and find an appropriate place/time.

Record the discussions using voice recorder/phone to later make transcripts for NVivo analysis and take notes.

Questions for elders

Explain project.

Date

Names, Ages, Consent (including request to take video)

1. Please could you tell us about the history of this place, its people and environment etc? (Probe: What are their thoughts? What did your grandparents tell you? Recent and more distant pasts?)
2. What were your grandparent's lives like? Can you tell us about their culture and spiritual beliefs especially relating to the forest?
3. Please tell us about the ancestors and clans (if this is felt to be appropriate to share)?
4. How do people here traditionally think about time (how does it flow? What are the seasons? How else did people traditionally observe long and short changes?)
5. How have the culture and beliefs here changed, especially about the forest and humans? And why?
6. Which are the culturally important plants, animals, phenomena (wind, thunder, hills, land etc), things?
7. Which plants, animals etc are now absent and which are new to the landscape?
8. How do you see the future unfolding here in the near future (e.g. 10, 20, 30 years) and in the more distant future (e.g. 50 or 100 years)? What are the different kinds of futures that are possible? (what if there was no tea) What are desired futures?
9. How would plants, animals, phenomena etc think about the future? What decisions would they make? Would these be different to humans? What do they need to thrive?

Activity 5: Stakeholder 'imaginary' interviews

[Drawing upon the stakeholder mapping by the TC for BE team and participatory landscape actor mapping conducted in planning sessions for WP5] **identify a group of 15-20 actors for interview** (may include a few community actors as well as secondary stakeholders). This does not need to be a representative sample, but it is a purposive selection to capture a broad range of landscape imaginaries.

Select interviewees to capture a diverse range of perspectives rather than a representative sample (e.g. urban, rural, tourists). Introduce the team, explain research objective and ask if people are willing to share feelings and thoughts regarding places and landscapes of the region. If they agree, proceed with the individual interview after requesting verbal consent to record the discussion and explain that data will be anonymized.

Criteria for selection of approx. 15–20 stakeholders could include landscape and value chain actors and 1 or 2 community representatives, but should present a wide range of imaginaries:

- Farmers, cooperatives, groups associations including, but not exclusively, export commodity production (avocado, tea, etc).
- Companies involved in selected commodities' commodity trade.
- Government (in land and resource use)
- Customary governance
- NGOs & CSOs– involved in biodiversity, equity & commodities
- Support and Service providers in export value chain
- Landowners and managers
- Members/leaders/funders of Sustainable landscape initiatives – SLIs and other sustainability value chain initiatives.
- Artists
- Tourists

Set up individual interviews. Use the semi-structured questionnaire below. Probe on the answers to get better understanding.

Explain project and obtain consent. Record for note-taking-purposes and take notes. Write up transcripts (full or bullet points? accurately fully and in the first person.

Questions for Stakeholder 'imaginary' interviews – Part 1

1. Name,
2. Member of group/ association/company/government etc Affiliation, role and number of years with organisation
3. How would you describe your relationship to the landscape?
4. What is your role, if any, in landscape decision-making? (If involved, probe on how the landscape is changing and key issues for communities and nature with respect to these changes)
5. What is your role, if any, in export commodity production? (If involved, probe on how the commodity sector is changing and key issues for communities and nature with respect to these changes)
6. How would you describe the history of this landscape? (probe on what have been the main changes and what and who have driven these changes)
7. What are the main socio-ecological challenges in the landscape?
8. What a) desirable and b) less desirable future trajectories for the landscape do you envision?
9. What might very radically different visions look like? How desirable are these for people and nature?
10. IF you could enact radically different future visions, what kind of changes would this require?
11. What kinds of actions or levers could be employed, and by whom, to achieve more desirable futures?
12. Please choose one 'wild' species (plant or animal) that is important to you in the landscape and explain why? What kind of future do you envision for this plant or animal? (repeat for feral and cultivated species)
13. What species are important for local communities do you think – important culturally, as well as for livelihoods and for nature itself?
14. Please choose one species (plant or animal) and explain what might be important to that species, what kind of futures it might like to see from its perspective?
15. How are these species affected by land use changes (including commodity driven changes) or other activities?
16. Is biodiversity being affected by land use changes and human activities? If so, how? (probe for different parts of the landscape e.g. plantations, smallholder agriculture, forest conservation areas, urban expansion etc).
17. **Photo exercise (see below)**

Continue the same interview with a participatory photography exercise, which asks participants to bring / share a photo showing what is meaningful about the landscape (minimum). You could also ask for photos showing the past, present and desirable futures if you feel there is willingness. Similarly, you

could ask for a photo of a species of plant or animal that is important to them and ask them to share this and discuss.

This approach uses an inductive, exploratory approach, minimizing issue framing as much as possible by asking for participants to provide their own responses to images, from which meanings can be derived (e.g. senses, cognitive, feelings, settings).

Record using phone or voicemail, ensure consent and take notes. Take captions if possible.

Stakeholder interview Part 2 – Participatory photography

Ask participants in advance to take or retrieve a handful of photos showing an area of the landscape that is meaningful / important to them.

Ask the participants what areas of the landscape they consider to be:

1. Special about the landscape
2. What they like about the landscape
3. What they dislike about the landscape
4. How they experience the landscape,
5. To indicate their favourite places, plants and animals
6. Invite to tell other stories about the landscape and how it is changing and what that means to them.

It may be possible, if the interviewee is enthusiastic, to ask for photos of the past and a desirable future as well, to expand the discussion on project themes.

Record the descriptions (statements) on your phone/ voice recorder.

Analysis of stakeholder interview transcripts

Taking the full transcripts, we will analyse these using Nvivo to explore how respondents talk about future visions, place frames and collective memories, **how they feel and experience the landscape, and multi-species priorities and perspectives.**

The photos should be chosen to reflect the diversity of sceneries or places in the landscape.

All statements should be transcribed and translated into English and edited (minor paraphrasing) for clarity. To code the statements, list all the terms in the transcripts and remove stop words (i.e. words of no interest, e.g. 'the'). Use a grounded theory approach in the content analysis (Strauss and Corbin, 1994) to analyse the imaginaries of participants, based on the emergence of repeated concepts.

Activity 5: Team review of lessons generated and planning for analysis and management of data.

Participatory team exercise to identify key insights and lessons from the fieldwork. Write up as a short note, guided by the key concepts, themes and questions of the research.

Agree on the structure of the files (see basecamp for how recordings, photos and notes have been organized and stored in the Kenya case).

Ensure all files are transferred to basecamp.

Develop a plan on how to write up each community-scale engagement and a timetable.

Agree on how to approach PV representatives to participate in SL workshop and how to support them, find appropriate venue for workshops etc and later feedback plans to communities.

See annex 4 for Kenya process followed.

Activity 6: Exhibition /community voices in multi-stakeholder social learning process

Invite a group of participants from the community-scale imaginaries work to present their imaginaries in an exhibition at the kick-off session of the social learning process.

Print photos and exhibit at the kick-off session for the workshop, alongside space for explanations and discussions.

There will also be a preparatory session to support the representatives from the community-scale PV group prior to the larger stakeholder meetings (2 days) to discuss the kick off workshop of the social learning and their expectations. It will be important to manage expectations, but also to hear their learning priorities and to support them to participate with more powerful actors and dominant perspectives.

**We may also plan to represent non-humans in the workshop as stakeholders (e.g. plants and animals being affected by commodity agriculture).

It may be possible to share photos from the stakeholder 'imaginary' interviews in the exhibition, although we are prioritizing more marginal perspectives. Under discussion.

Annex 1: Ethics & Consent forms

Participant Information Sheet

The Transformative Change in Telecoupled Agro-food systems for Biodiversity and Equity (TCforBE) project (2022–26) is funded by the European Union. The project addresses the following challenge: Increasing demand for agricultural commodities such as soya, palm oil, avocados, tea and cocoa in the European Union is driving land use changes and deforestation in many sourcing locations, leading to biodiversity losses, as well as other social and environmental impacts. The EU is seeking to reduce these impacts and its new policies such as Farm to Fork will influence future EU and producer country trade and has potential implications for employment, livelihoods as well as biodiversity and nature in the landscapes where commodities are grown. The EU has funded this action-research project to support the exploration of transformative change pathways with landscape, national and EU / international actors. The project recognises that there are plural perspectives on what transformative change in food and agriculture systems could be. The project is exploring with diverse actors, especially those at community and landscape level in selected landscapes in Kenya, Colombia and Cameroon, as well as EU and national decision-makers, on how the landscapes are changing, the significant barriers to positive change, and a range of potential desirable landscape futures for people and nature. We will also explore diverse levers such as governance levers such as sustainable landscape initiatives, legal, consumer, and financial mechanisms for achieving change, as well as shifting narratives by communities and social movements.

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Partners

Participant Consent Form

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

To be completed by the participant. If the participant is under 18, separate consent forms should be completed by the participant and by their parent / guardian. An age-appropriate version of the consent form may need to be produced for participants under 18.

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• I have read the information sheet about this study.• I have had an opportunity to ask questions and discuss this study.• I have received satisfactory answers to all my questions.• I have received enough information about this study.• I understand that I am / the participant is free to withdraw from this study:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ At any time (until such date as this will no longer be possible, which I have been told)○ Without giving a reason for withdrawing• I agree to my / the participant's contribution being recorded (if the study involves recording)• I agree to take part in this study• We may wish to use your research data for a further project in anonymous form. If you agree to this, please tick here <input type="checkbox"/>	
Signed (participant)	Date
Participant name in block letters	
Signed (parent / guardian) (if participant is under 18)	Date
Parent/guardian name in block letters	
Signature of researcher	Date
Researcher's name and contact details (including telephone number and e-mail address):	

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM – PHOTOS FOR SPECIFIC USES

To be completed by the participant. If the participant is under 18, separate consent forms should be completed by the participant and by their parent / guardian. An age-appropriate version of the consent form may need to be produced for participants under 18.

Proposed uses of photos and captions:

- To support participant exploration on the study themes in discussion with the research team.
- As part of discussions with wider CFA members, facilitated by the research team.
- To be shared and discussed as part of multi-stakeholder discussions later in the project.
- To be shared in peer reviewed articles and project briefing papers.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It has been explained to me what the project seeks to do and the intended uses for the photos and captions. • I have had an opportunity to ask questions and discuss these proposed uses for the photos and captions. • I have received satisfactory answers to all my questions. • I have received enough information about this study. • I understand that I am / the participant is free to withdraw from this study: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ At any time (until such date as this will no longer be possible, which I have been told) ○ Without giving a reason for withdrawing ○ However, I also note that if photos are shared on the internet, it is not possible to remove them once they are shared • I agree to my / the participant's contribution being recorded (if the study involves recording) • I agree to take part in this study • We may wish to use your research data for a further project in anonymous form. If you agree to this, please tick here 	
Signed (participant)	Date
Participant name in block letters	
Signed (parent / guardian) (if participant is under 18)	Date
Parent/guardian name in block letters	
Signature of researcher	Date
Researcher's name and contact details (including telephone number and e-mail address):	

Annex 2: Selection of community groups or associations – Kenyan example

Table 1: Initially selected CFAs

	CFA	LOCATION	REASON FOR SELECTION
1.	Mara Mara	Bomet County	Tea growing area
2.	Nyangores	Bomet County (Location), Narok County (Administratively)	Tea and avocado growing area
3.	Nairotia (Berur Cooperative)	Bomet County (geographical location), Narok County (Administratively)	Tea and avocado growing area
4.	Kiptunga	Nakuru County	Presence of Ogiek tribal group

Table 2: Mau Forest Compartments

Forest Compartment	Forest Block	Location-County	CFA	Ethnic Groups adjacent to the forest	Major economic activities
South Western Mau	Mara Mara , , Ndoinet, Itare, Kericho	Kericho and Bomet	Mara Mara CFA	Predominantly Kipsigis and Ogiek. Other ethnic groups residing in forest fringes include Gikuyu and Kisii.	Crop farming-tea Livestock, Beekeeping
Transmara Forest Reserve	Nyangores , Nairotia & Olenguruone	Bomet& Narok	Nyangores& Nairotia	Kipsigis	Crop farming- Tea, (Horticultural crops” avocado and onions pyrethrum farming) & Livestock farming.
Eastern Mau	Kiptunga , Likia, Logoman Sururu, Mariashoni, Baraget. Nessuit, Teret& Elburgon(Exicision)	Nakuru	Kiptunga	Ogiek, Kikuyu, Maasai & Kipsigis	Crop farming and livestock keeping. Crops grown include potatoes, maize and pyrethrum.

Maasai Mau	Comprises of 1 Bloc, managed by County Government of Narok on behalf of the people.	Narok County	No information about existence of a CFA. The area has been abit volatile due to previous eviction exercise, but I got to learn that the situation has improved of late	Maasai Kalenjin (Kipsigis& Tugen) and Ndorobo	Livestock keeping and crop farming (potatoes, maize, peas)
Western Mau	Masaita, Kerisoi, Londiani	Kericho County		Kipsigis and Kisiis and Agikuyu	Pyrethrum, potatoes, wheat, and Tea, and Livestock: cows and sheep)
Southern Mau (128 Ha)	Narok South	Olposimoru and Mau Narok		Maasais	Wheat, pulses (Peas), onions, Livestock (cows and shoats
Olposimoru,	Olposimoru CFA	Narok		Maasai, Kipsigis, and Ogiek	Beekeeping, livestock and crop farming (Wheat and peas)
Maunarok (808.09)				Maasai, Agikuyu, Kalenjin and Ogiek	Beekeeping, livestock and crop farming (Wheat and peas)

Annex 4: Developing a pre-fieldwork Plan for the week (Kenya example)

Plan for fieldwork 'pilot' week		Roles
Friday pm	<p>Inform CFA leaders Welcome, introductions Introduction to project Selection process (this can be complex, in Kenya we invited 30 people from CFA and asked for volunteers, but then from these selected 10 covering gender, user groups etc. We asked them to find non-CFA representatives living nearby. The rest were invited to FGDs. Agree on next steps (including reaching non-CFAs through snowball) Interview community leaders as key informants (optional) Agree FGD invitations etc</p>	<p>Allocate roles in the team for introductions, who will take notes, who will record, who will keep time.</p> <p>These roles can change but it makes sense to split and get to know individuals in the PV work.</p>
Sat am	Work at Town campus	
Monday 8.30 am	<p>Re-introduce project</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) Technical talk on using and managing camera (20 mins) b) Photo reflection (look at photos and discuss, then organize by fear and hope). Split into 3 groups to do exercise and then come back as a group (15 mins) c) Treasure hunt <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Take photos of favourite colour, portrait, pattern, a hidden detail (15 mins?) - Split into 2 groups – one person takes card out and transfers photos to laptop/tablet and discuss (15 mins) d) Explain activity 1 (e.g. questions 1 and 2?) Please take 2 or 3 photos which show what this place / community / environment / area / forest means to you and what you care about? (20 mins) You can take more, but choose 2 or 3 to share tomorrow. 	
Tuesday am	<p>Meet PV group - Sit in a big group and ask how was the experience? Explain what we are going to do. Reassure. Ground rules: non-judgemental, have fun, learning from each other with respect, can have different views, no right or wrong, not just pretty photos but getting meaningful ones. Consent form.</p> <p>Split into groups of 3 or 4.</p>	

	<p>Discuss with individuals how they got in, look at quite a few of their photos, ask for the best 2 or 3. Copy all the photos to participant sub-folder (all) and pick 3 favourites to copy and paste into the sub-folder (using control c and control v)</p> <p>Then share in groups of 3 to discuss what photos they took and why. (record discussion).</p> <p>Develop and record captions.</p> <p>Go back into big group, with 1 photo shared from each of the smaller groups for discussion and reflection. Explain summary of overall process</p> <p>Set 'activity' 2: Please 2 or 3 photos for each of the following for this place/environment:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The past - The present - Expected future (near future and far future) - Desired future (what you would like to see more of in near future and far future) 	
Tuesday	<p>FGDs – CFA groups</p> <p>Split into two groups with 2 facilitators each – one facilitates and one takes notes and records. 1.5 to 2 hours. Record using recorders. Develop and record captions.</p> <p>They will get copies of their favourites at the end of the week (Thursday). We can offer 1 family photo as a thank you?</p>	
Wed am	<p>Meet PV group – Sit in a big group and ask how was the experience? Explain what we are going to do. Reassure. Ground rules: non-judgemental, have fun, learning from each other with respect, can have different views, no right or wrong, not just pretty photos but getting meaningful ones. Consent form.</p> <p>Split into groups of 3 or 4.</p> <p>Discuss with individuals how they got in, look at quite a few of their photos, ask for the best 2 or 3.</p>	

	<p>Copy all the photos to participant sub-folder (all) and pick 3 favourites to copy and paste into the sub-folder (using control c and control v)</p> <p>Then share in groups of 3 to discuss what photos they took and why. (record discussion) Develop and record captions.</p> <p>Go back into big group, with 1 photo shared from each of the smaller groups for discussion and reflection. Explain summary of overall process</p> <p>Set 'activity 3'</p> <p>Activity 3:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Choose a plant, animal or feature that from this environment / forest / area that is meaningful to you and then take a photo, make a drawing, find a symbol, find on google, clipping from newspaper (in the explanation you can say it may be an ongoing spiritual connection, an ongoing relationship, significant encounter, etc) b) Think how the plant / animal / feature is experiencing change and ask the participant to take a photo to represent how the plant/animal/feature feels and experiences that change? c) What different decisions would the animal / plant / feature (e.g. river, mountain etc) make if they were in charge? (discussion, rather than photo assignment) 	
Wed pm	FGDs – non-CFA groups	
Thurs am	<p>Split into groups of 3 or 4.</p> <p>Discuss with individuals how they got in, look at quite a few of their photos, ask for the best 2 or 3.</p> <p>Copy all the photos to participant sub-folder (all) and pick 3 favourites to copy and paste into the sub-folder (using control c and control v)</p> <p>Then share in groups of 3 to discuss what photos they took and why. (record discussion)</p> <p>Go back into big group, with 1 photo shared from each of the smaller groups for discussion and reflection. Explain summary of overall process</p>	

	<p>Agree consent (go through the uses of the photos and ask if they are happy with the proposed uses and check for any sensitivities, do consent).</p> <p>Sharing in the PV group (possibly wider community but that needs thought by the research team if it is appropriate). Put printed photos on the wall with caption as an exhibition. Could make a little celebration? Discuss the photos as a group and reflect on what they have learned during the week (make sure to capture this).</p> <p>Discuss next steps (explain invite to multi-stakeholder social learning)</p>	
	<p>Elders' storytelling session here</p> <p>Please can you tell us some stories about the ancestors and spirits of the place? (give some indication of time)</p> <p>Discuss</p> <p>[record and video? if they consent]</p>	
Friday am	<p>Writing up session</p> <p>Agree on how to write up transcripts from recordings, and notes from PV process and FGDs.</p> <p>Agree on report outline</p> <p>Discussion on next steps</p>	

Annex 5: Post-fieldwork plan to support write up, analysis and community feedback

	Who	When	How
1. Mara Mara Community Write up and Analysis			
Reflect upon what we learned (participatory exercise – surprising / key trends, TC, method)	All VN to write up findings	9.02.2024	Write up and share
2. Organising materials			
Organise voice recordings into correctly labelled folders & upload to <u>basecamp</u> . <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 sets of activities with PV group x 11 people • caption discussions / narrations • FGDs x 4 • Elders' discussion 	George to set up	Asap before forget	Set up folders on Basecamp All to upload by 16 th Feb latest
Check all PV photos are organized in correct folders and uploaded to <u>basecamp</u> .	As above		
Write up transcripts from PV individual discussions (3 activities x 11 people) and caption discussion, narration, and upload to <u>basecamp</u> .		By end Feb.	
Write up transcripts from FGDs x 4 etc		By end Feb.	
Any modifications to plan for week	<i>Discussion of plan for the week – we agreed the following:</i> Pre-visit 1a – meet and interview CFA officials and chiefs (Thurs) Pre-visit 1b – to do selection (week before) and present project (fri)		

	<p>Day 1 (mon) camera training and share activity 1 task, FGDs (CFA)</p> <p>Day 2 (tues) Activity 1 sharing and explain Activity 2, FGDs (non-CFA)</p> <p>Day 3 (wed) Activity 2 sharing and explain Activity 3, elders storytelling.</p> <p>Day 4: (thurs) Activity 3 sharing, (gap for any activities not done), initial small group sharing and agree on who would share more widely.</p> <p>Day 5: exhibition, discussion, reflection (maybe with larger group)</p>		
Analysis of qualitative material (NVivo)	Valerie to explore Nvivo training options	In next 2 weeks	
3. Selection of CFAs and criteria			
	Dorothy to extend the table with more options, descriptions etc	By 16 th Feb	
4. Stakeholder interviews	<p>Valerie to improve proposed method</p> <p>Share with team and discuss</p> <p>Prioritise a set of actors with diverse reviews</p>	By 16 th Feb	
5. Planning timetable for CFAs implementation, next steps for delivery of PV report – draft and review process	<p>Community 2 by x</p> <p>Write up by x</p> <p>Community 3 by x</p> <p>Write up by x</p> <p>Community 4 by x</p> <p>Write up by x</p> <p>Nvivo analysis and draft of community analysis</p>	To be confirmed by the team	

	Report draft end April		
6. Discuss some ideas for report format		To be confirmed by the team	
7. Discussion on community participation in social learning and community feedback, overall social learning plans	No of community participants to be confirmed after review of CFA selection and budgets.	To be confirmed – VN, VI, JH/JH	
8. Equipment	16GB SD cards Bag to keep together. Voice recorders Discuss how much cost is for printing of photos		

Annex 6: Overall timetable for imaginaries work (example Kenya)

Plan for the rural imaginaries work	Dates for implementation & delivery	Who / what
Community 1 fieldwork Conduct first round of fieldwork in Mara Mara – photovoice and FGDs	Fieldwork from 2 nd Feb to 9 th of Feb	
Reflect and pull together a write-up (to be agreed how)	Report write-up by Feb 23 rd	
Conduct analysis		
Community 2 fieldwork Conduct first round of fieldwork in x – photovoice and FGDs		
Reflect and pull together a write-up (to be agreed how)		
Conduct analysis		
Community 3 fieldwork Conduct first round of fieldwork in x – photovoice and FGDs		
Reflect and pull together a write-up (to be agreed how)		
Conduct analysis		
Community 4 fieldwork Conduct first round of fieldwork in x – photovoice and FGDs		
Reflect and pull together a write-up (to be agreed how)		
Conduct analysis		
Conduct stakeholder interviews		
Analysis of all inputs into final report		

Annex 7: Semi-structured interview questions for community leaders (optional)

Questions planned for Kenya community work (not yet undertaken though)

Chief (name, details, consent)

1. What are the changes in the place / area including environment?
2. What are the main causes of socio-ecological change?
3. How was the place / environment different in the past?
4. What are the key interventions focused on the place / environment? (Probe on the landscape initiative)
5. What are the challenges you face in relation to the place / environment?
6. What are the social challenges you face?
7. What do you expect the future to be like?
8. What would you like the future to be like?
9. How is export production changing and why? What are its impacts?
10. Any questions for us?

CFA lead (name, details, consent)

1. Name, length of time with the CFA
2. History of the CFA
3. Governance and structure of the CFA including the user groups
4. Achievements and challenges of the CFA / for different user groups
5. Previous and ongoing interventions on environment, forests, agriculture
6. Future plans for the CFA
7. Trends and changes and causes of change.
8. Involvement of and relations with other stakeholders and partners
9. Any questions for us?

Annex 8: Arts-based research in Cameroon

For national and landscape scale in Cameroon we are seeking creativity and innovation to foster creative thinking and innovative problem-solving. We invited an artist to collaborate and explore alternative perspectives, challenge the to existing assumptions of the Cameroon research team, generate new, visual ideas, and provide and unconventional and alternative (non-written) way of representing and communicating our ongoing research findings.

The artist Mekouti (Thierry Mekoa, director of [Gallery Art AfroBantu](#) in Yaounde) was invited to participate based on previous artistic collaboration with the TC4BE project coordinator Verina.

First, we explained the TC4BE project, the cocoa value chain and landscape from our academic perspective. We then listened to the artists perspective on the cocoa value chain from Cameroon to Europe.

Second, the artist visited, with members of the team, one main cocoa growing area around Ntui, in the Centre region of Cameroon, and then the Dja landscape, the TC4BE selected Innovation Landscape, so that he can see how cocoa is produced differently and different cultural contexts. He was present during the Landscape imaginaries activity and helped capture the process and discussion with photos and an artwork. A drawn imaginary was created with the participants of the photo voice exercise.

Third, based on the artists interactions with cocoa farming households, traders, government officials and Cameroonian and European chocolate consumers in Cameroon, he formed ideas for how to visualize. The artist was supported to purchase materials and began the artwork. At different times since 2023 researchers, consumers, farmers, cocoa traders have been invited to the gallery to discuss and for those who are interested, to join in creating the artwork. The discussions result in further co-creation of the artwork.

In parallel, fourthly, the artwork is at a stage where it can be exhibited, with an explanatory text and accompanying dialogues. This has taken place at the Gallery in Yaounde, via [Facebook](#), [Instagram](#), and [Linked In](#). The artwork was exhibited by Mâ_Epicerie Fine, a stakeholder in the Cameroon value chain in the has recently opened new boutique supermarket and restaurant offering high quality, "100% Made in Cameroon" products, a new trend and concept in the country. It was also exhibited on 21 May 2024, Cameroon's Independence Day and national holiday at the Presidential Palace of Etoudi. This multimodal communication with visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and performative elements helps to enhance the accessibility and reach of the research and means we engage with different stakeholders, sharing their perspectives and values about cocoa and chocolate and engage with a wider audience, including those who may not be traditionally involved or interested in academic research, thus fostering broader societal impact. We are noting reactions of people to the artwork, and incorporating these into the ongoing artwork until it is physically "full", saturation point is reached 9ie no more different values are heard. It will continue to be enriched as outputs of the project become available, and used as part of national dialogues. We hope for an exchange visit of the artist to TC4BE teams in UK and or Europe to continue the process.

